

PLAYFUL CITY JAM

Dr. Valentina Vezzani

Research Fellow, School of Design, University of Leeds (UK)

✉ texvv@leeds.ac.uk

Dr. Tang Tang

Lecturer in Sustainable Design, School of Design, University of Leeds (UK)

✉ T.X.Tang@leeds.ac.uk

Fabrizio Pierandrei

CEO of PACO Design Collaborative (IT)

✉ fabrizio@pacollaborative.com

BACKGROUND ISSUES

On the occasion of the 2014 “Design and Emotion” Conference, Dr. Vezzani and Dr. Tang, from the University of Leeds, will work with Fabrizio Pierandrei from PACO to organize a one-day (6 hours) workshop aimed at using design thinking as leverage to create a sustainable urban community in Medellín. It attempts to test a portable model to engage stakeholders in the use of Design Jams for the development of a sustainable community.

Playful City Jam calls for the participation of Medellín communities and local organizations to work creatively and collaboratively with practitioners and students from different design areas (i.e., design students and teachers with social sensibility, government workers, community groups involved with social innovation processes, etc.) to deliver multi-sectorial solutions to promoting a sense of community and individual engagement in urban sustainability.

This proposed workshop, which is part of an ongoing project led by Dr. Tang and Dr. Vezzani, focuses on developing a design-led model and tools to enable the active participation of both individuals and local communities in sustainable living and therefore enhance their sense of community¹.

Previous experiences of running both global and local design jams in Leeds (in partnership with PACO) have resulted in a

1 McMillan, D. and Chavis, D. M. (1986) *Sense of Community: a Definition and Theory*, *Journal of Community Psychology*, Vol. 14, pp. 6-21.

“prototype” for applying collaborative design in the improvement of community living. *Playful City Jam* will test the effectiveness of the “prototype” developed in enhancing creativity and supporting spontaneous design activities, aiding an interdisciplinary group to work together on problem identification, design ideation, prototyping and implementation.

WORKSHOP GOALS

Playful City Jam focuses on a Medellín urban community and the theme of sustainable lifestyle; in particular, the attendees will be asked to work in team on a particular challenge of Medellín. This challenge will be suggested by Medellín Ciudad Inteligente² and will be kept secret until the Jam kick-off.

The aim of the proposed workshop is threefold:

- To test and evaluate the effectiveness of using *Design Jams* to engage urban communities, local (administrative) organizations and designers to co-produce solutions to urban sustainability and community development;
- To test the level of public interest and engagement in a *Design Jam* and assess participant feedback, knowledge and the skills they acquire to act on the issues related to sustainability after the jam.

2 <http://mdeinteligente.co/estrategia/>

- To contribute to the development of a portable model that would enable local administrative bodies to engage local citizens, organizations and design practitioners in the dialogue on sustainable community development. The aim is to produce innovative ideas and solutions starting from needs, expectations and knowledge of citizens involved themselves in the urban community for the co-creation of social innovations of real value for individuals and communities.

APPROACH: A DESIGN JAM

Playful City Jam is a design jam, planned and implemented by two organizations, by bringing different interests, resources and approaches together:

School of Design, University of Leeds (UK), represented by Dr. Tang and Dr. Vezzani, leading the study on sustainable design education and collaborative design. Co-organizers of the Global Sustainability and Service Jams³ in Leeds.

PACO Design Collaborative; a non-profit association for social promotion located in Milan (Italy), as an international network of holistic professionals and organizations, who believe in the potential of design and education to foster social innovation, sustainable behaviors and business opportunities. PACO is the local organizer of the Global Sustainability, Service, and Gov Jams in Milan. <http://pacollaborative.com>

Medellín Ciudad Inteligente; a program of the Medellín Mayorality and UNE EPM Telecomunicaciones (Colombia) that works on open government, citizen participation, social innovation, and sustainability. Its aim is to improve the quality of life of citizens through digital inclusion as well as citizens' empowerment and engagement. <http://estrategia.medellin.co>

The *Playful City Jam* aims to involve and activate different types of stakeholders who will co-produce tangible design outcomes on Medellín's real challenges. It is based on collaboration, sharing, inclusion, experimentation and fun. These characteristics will allow the attendees in Medellín to overcome their social and cultural barriers, to engage in discussions and understand common problems, to learn from one another, and to transform their ideas into a concrete design or plan of action which can become real.

The *Playful City Jam* will be based on the direct participation of:

- One of the Organizers: as coordinator and observer of all the activities along the jam;
- Jammers: working in team; at least one of them will be a designer;
- Facilitators: preferably designers who will be able to facilitate the dialogue within each team and the use of the tools provided, to give insights and tips during each phase of the jam;

³ To know more about the Global Jams visit: <http://planet.globalservicejam.org/content/about> and <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLjJM-jp5eYYXIEcDJsABfhO4zYhkqe2fC>

- Mentors: invited speakers who are familiar with the topics proposed at the jam. They do not have to be there all day, but should talk to every team and attend their final presentations.

The *Playful City Jam* will be structured according to the following phases and activities:

1. Welcome: the organizer will present the goals and schedule of the jam, and introduce the staff as support of the activities; mentors will be invited to provide quick insights and tips on Medellín's challenge suggested by Medellín Ciudad Inteligente) to be developed during the jam.
2. Warm-up: a game will be proposed to the attendees (including facilitators and mentors) to break the barriers among people and prepare them for teamwork.
3. Rainstorming and exploration: with the support of facilitators, jammers will cluster in teams and start to research and discuss the proposed challenge, starting from their experiences and interests.
4. Sharing ideas: each team will make a quick presentation of its own theme, ideas, and approach to overcome challenge. To allow teams to compare their processes and bounce off ideas to each other, they could share what they have done in the interim presentation before the lunch break.
5. Coffee/Lunch break: this phase will allow the teams to have a break, change focus, and continue the dialogue in and across teams.
6. Designing the idea: the teams will be provided with service design tools to support the development and communication of their idea, including a business canvas, and create prototypes, as tangible evidences of what to be implemented.
7. Final presentations: each team will present its own project, and a final discussion on the experience will be opened

During the jam, some activities and short interviews will be recorded by a video camera. Questionnaires will be used to assess attendees' expectations, personal interests, and feedbacks on the process and tools provided. Semi-structured interviews will be conducted to gather feedback from attendees on their engagement in the activities.

CONCLUSION / FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

The Playful City Jam in Medellín is an opportunity for the School of Design, Leeds University and PACO Design Collaborative to strengthen the collaboration with Medellín Ciudad Inteligente. It will open a way to further international longer-term projects on collaborative design for sustainability and social innovation.

Moreover, the workshop outcomes will be disseminated through the publication of academic journals.

Characteristics of the space/room needed to conduct the workshop

The space with moving tables and chairs should allow people to move easily, considering the planned activities. In particular, each team (from 3 to 6 people per each) will need a desk, chairs and ideally wall space.

- Space to project kick-off slides and video clips
- WiFi: stable and fast connection for all attendees.
- Coffee breaks: a room with enough space to create an area for coffee break and “relax”.
- Lunch break: preferably in another space (maybe outdoors) to allow attendees to change their focus, enjoy the social meeting and strengthen relations. If not a refreshment service in another place, a take-away would be an alternative.

Materials and special requirements

Movable tables (for working in teams) and chairs; projector; WiFi; stationery such as paper (A3 and/or A2), sticky notes, markers, scissors, tape, glue, cardboard.

Video camera with tripod and memory card to film some of the workshop activities and short interviews.

Refreshments: coffee, tea, juices, snacks and preferably also some sandwiches for the lunch break.

Communication of the event

The Playful City Jam event will have visibility online through the Playful School Project web page, hosted by the School of Design, University of Leeds website. Moreover, PACO and Medellín Ciudad Inteligente will promote the event on their own websites.

We will set up a project blog that will record the workshop, e.g., procedures and status updates, and a Twitter and Facebook page that will promote the event and involve the attendees before, during and after the Playful City Jam experience.